

Assessment Of Occupational Safety Knowledge and Infection Prevention Practices Among *Harijan* Sweepers in Rajshahi, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) are a global health concern, yet the role of non-clinical staff, particularly Harijan sweepers, remains underexplored. These workers face daily exposure to infection risks, unsafe waste handling, and inadequate protective measures. **Objectives:** To evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of Harijan sweepers at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), Bangladesh, regarding HAIs, waste management, and occupational safety. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 110 Harijan sweepers at RMCH (January–March 2024). Data were collected using a structured Bengali questionnaire and an observational checklist. Descriptive statistics, ANOVA, Pearson's correlation, and odds ratios (95% CI) were analysed using SPSS v24. **Results:** The participants were predominantly Hindu (92.73%) and female (64.6%) and ranged in age from 41 to 60 years (61.8%). Knowledge was moderate in 60.9%, poor in 27.3%, and good in 11.8%. Attitudes were moderate in 64.6%, but practices were poor in 61.8%. Only 2.7% segregated waste correctly, 17.3% used puncture-resistant sharps containers, and 16.4% disinfected PPE. More than half (52.7%) reported needle-stick injuries. KAP domains were positively correlated ($r = 0.327$ – 0.612) but not statistically significant. **Conclusion:** Harijan sweepers demonstrated moderate knowledge and attitudes but poor infection control practices. Interventions, including training, PPE provision, supervision, and safer waste systems, are urgently needed to protect cleaners and reduce HAIs.

Keywords: Occupational knowledge, Occupational safety, Harijan sweepers, Infection prevention, Rajshahi.

INTRODUCTION

Occupational safety knowledge is a critical determinant of workers' ability to identify, minimise, and manage risks associated with hazardous hospital environments. Effective infection prevention practices, including the consistent use of personal protective equipment, adherence to hand hygiene, and proper biomedical waste management, are essential to reducing hospital-acquired infections and safeguarding both staff and patients. Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), also referred to as nosocomial infections, are infections that patients acquire while receiving care in healthcare facilities and were neither present nor incubating at the time of admission [1]. HAIs pose a major challenge to healthcare systems worldwide, leading to increased

morbidity, mortality, prolonged hospital stays, and a substantial financial burden on both patients and healthcare institutions [2]. While much attention has been given to clinical healthcare workers in infection prevention, non-clinical staff, particularly cleaning personnel, play a critical role in maintaining hospital hygiene and controlling infection transmission [3, 4]. *Harijan* sweepers are responsible for tasks such as floor cleaning, waste collection, handling of sharps and medical equipment, and maintaining sanitation in high-risk areas such as operating theatres and intensive care units. Despite the crucial role they play, *Harijan* sweepers are often under-recognised in institutional safety policies and may lack adequate knowledge, practical skills, and access to resources, leaving them vulnerable to occupational hazards [5, 6].

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The *Harijan* community in Rajshahi is one of the most marginalised caste-based groups in Bangladesh, often identified as “untouchables,” with many members engaged in sanitation, cleaning, and waste-collection occupations. [7, 8]. Studies of their socio-economic conditions show that most *Harijans* have only primary education (about 41.8%), while significant proportions work as scavengers (42.4%) or cobblers (27.7%), reflecting limited livelihood options dependent on low-status tasks [9, 10]. Their living conditions are crowded in small colonies (*Pallis*) with poor housing, inadequate sanitation, and frequent struggles for basic infrastructure; an acute accommodation crisis is reported in all *Harijan Pallis* in Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Children attend school despite obstacles, showing educational aspirations, but unemployment remains high, especially among educated youths, who face both economic and social discrimination tied to their identity [9]. Cultural stigma persists: *Harijans* often experience exclusion in public places, discrimination in employment beyond traditional roles, and face barriers to equality despite constitutional guarantees [11]. In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) like Bangladesh, the risks faced by hospital *Harijan* sweepers are exacerbated by limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and high patient loads. Studies have consistently demonstrated that *Harijan* sweepers in LMICs frequently encounter blood-borne pathogens, chemical disinfectants, and improperly disposed sharps without sufficient training or personal protective equipment (PPE) [1, 7]. Inadequate adherence to proper infection control measures, including hand hygiene, PPE use, safe handling of infectious waste, and disinfection of reusable equipment, can increase the risk of HAIs both for healthcare personnel and patients. Evidence from similar settings indicates that knowledge deficits, poor training, and lack of institutional support are major barriers to safe practice among hospital *Harijan* sweepers [2, 8]. Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), established in 1958, is one of the largest and most prominent government hospitals in northern Bangladesh. As a tertiary care centre, RMCH provides advanced medical services, including specialised diagnostic facilities and high-capacity inpatient care. The hospital employs a substantial cleaning workforce responsible for maintaining hygiene across wards, laboratories, operating theatres,

and other patient care areas. *Harijan* sweepers are exposed to a wide range of occupational hazards, including contact with infectious materials, blood-borne pathogens, and improperly segregated waste. The city of Rajshahi, known as the “Clean and Green City” of Bangladesh, is recognised for its educational institutions, historic architecture, lush mango orchards, and environmental initiatives. Despite this reputation for cleanliness, hospital-based occupational health and safety remains an area requiring systematic evaluation and improvement.

Many studies highlight that knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) among hospital *Harijan* sweepers regarding HAIs and waste management are often inadequate. A study in Indian tertiary hospitals found that *Harijan* sweepers were aware of occupational risks but had limited technical knowledge and inconsistent adherence to safe practices [2, 9]. Socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, and years of service had limited influence on infection control behaviours, emphasising the importance of training and institutional reinforcement rather than relying solely on personal characteristics [10]. Globally, *Harijan* sweepers are particularly vulnerable to sharps injuries and exposure to blood-borne pathogens, underscoring the need for structured interventions to improve safety compliance [12, 13]. Attitudes toward occupational safety among *Harijan* sweepers are often more positive than their knowledge or practices. For example, many workers recognise the general risks associated with hospital work and the importance of gloves, handwashing, and waste management; however, this awareness does not always translate into correct and consistent behaviours [13]. Compliance with infection control practices is influenced by multiple factors, including availability of PPE, access to handwashing stations, workload, supervision, and periodic training. Without institutional support and reinforcement, even motivated staff may struggle to maintain safe practices consistently [14, 15]. KAP surveys provide a structured approach to assessing knowledge, attitudes, and practices among healthcare personnel, allowing researchers to identify gaps, evaluate risk behaviours, and inform the development of targeted interventions. By assessing the KAP of the *Harijan* sweepers at RMCH, it is possible to determine areas where training is needed, identify unsafe practices,

and provide recommendations to strengthen institutional policies and occupational safety programs. Understanding these aspects is critical not only for protecting the *Harijan* sweepers themselves but also for preventing the transmission of HAIs within the hospital environment, ultimately benefiting patient safety and public health.

This study aims to evaluate the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding HAIs, waste management, and occupational safety among *Harijan* sweepers at RMCH, Bangladesh. Additionally, the study seeks to identify predictors of safe practices and occupational risk behaviours, thereby providing evidence for interventions that can improve both workplace safety and infection control in resource-constrained healthcare settings. By focusing on this often-overlooked workforce, the study contributes to a growing body of literature emphasising the importance of non-clinical staff in hospital infection prevention programs and occupational health initiatives.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Design and Setting

A cross-sectional quantitative study was conducted to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) regarding hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), waste management, and occupational safety among *Harijan* sweepers at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), Bangladesh. RMCH, established in 1958, is one of the largest government hospitals in northern Bangladesh, providing tertiary care services, advanced diagnostics, and training for medical professionals. The study was carried out between January and March 2024.

2.2 Study Population and Sample

The study population included all *Harijan* sweepers employed at RMCH during the study period. A total of 120 *Harijan* sweepers met the inclusion criteria, which required participants to be 18 years or older, engaged in active cleaning duties, and employed on a permanent or long-term basis. Out of these, 110 consented to participate, representing 91.7% of the eligible population. *Harijan* sweepers who refused to participate were excluded. The sampling method

employed was a census of all available staff meeting the inclusion criteria.

2.3 Data Collection Tools and Procedures

Harijan sweepers were contacted through in-person visits by the research team. The study objectives were explained, and informed consent was obtained. Questionnaires were distributed, and participants were given three weeks to complete them. Researchers followed up to ensure timely completion and assisted as needed. Non-respondents after repeated follow-ups were excluded. Observational verification of practices, including PPE use, hand hygiene, and waste handling, was conducted discretely to minimise response bias.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and observational checklist, developed based on a review of existing literature. The questionnaire was divided into five sections:

1. Socio-demographic characteristics: 6 items including age, gender, religion, marital status, years of service, and monthly income.
2. Knowledge: 9 open-ended questions assessing understanding of HAIs, waste management, and occupational risks.
3. Attitude: 9 questions using a Likert-scale and Yes/No responses to evaluate perceptions of occupational risk and safety practices.
4. Practice: 10 questions on self-reported behaviours, supplemented by observational verification of hand hygiene, PPE use, and waste handling.
5. Safety behaviour: Observational checklist recording proper use of PPE, hand hygiene, and correct waste segregation procedures.

The questionnaire was translated into Bengali and English, with all participants choosing Bengali for their responses. Researchers assisted participants with questionnaire completion when necessary.

2.4 Data Management and Analysis

Completed questionnaires were coded and entered into Microsoft Excel for cleaning and preliminary management. Data were analysed using SPSS version 24. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages, summarised continuous and categorical variables. Normality of continuous variables was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to determine differences between groups, and Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to examine relationships among knowledge, attitude, and practice scores. Odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated for categorical risk factors. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$.

Responses were scored to classify participants into Low, Medium, or High KAP levels. The scoring system was as follows:

1. Knowledge: 80–100% correct = High; 50–79% = Medium; <50% = Low.
2. Attitude: Scored on a 2-point system (correct = 2, unsure = 1, incorrect = 0) with total scores categorized similarly.
3. Practice: Self-reported and observed behaviours scored on the same 2-point system, classified as Low, Medium, or High.

The assessment framework consists of four domains—knowledge, attitude, practice, and safety behaviour—each evaluated through distinct methods with specific scoring or observation criteria. Knowledge is assessed using a questionnaire that combines multiple-choice and open-ended questions, with performance classified as low, medium, or high. Attitude is measured through Likert-scale ratings or simple yes/no responses, also categorised into low, medium, or high levels. Practice is evaluated either through self-reports or direct observation, again scored as low, medium, or high. Finally, safety behaviour is assessed using an observational checklist

focusing on key aspects such as personal protective equipment (PPE) use, hand hygiene, and waste handling practices. This structured approach provides a comprehensive way to measure not only what participants know but also their attitudes, actual practices, and adherence to essential safety behaviours.

2.5 Ethical Considerations

The study commenced after obtaining ethical approval from the RMCH authority. The list of *Harijan* sweepers and their contact details was obtained from the HRM section of RMCH. All the study participants were asked to sign a written consent form before participating in this study.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Socio-demographic characteristics

A total of 110 *Harijan* sweepers participated in the study at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), Bangladesh. Of the respondents, 71 (64.6%) were female and 39 (35.5%) were male, indicating that the majority of hospital *Harijan* sweepers were women. Concerning religion, Hindu workers constituted the largest group (92.73%), followed by Christians (7.27%). Analysis of marital status revealed that more than half of the participants were married (50.9%), while 40.9% were unmarried and 8.2% were divorced, widowed, or separated. Length of service varied: 52 participants (47.3%) had worked between 1 and 10 years, whereas 58 participants (52.7%) had more than 10 years of service, reflecting a relatively experienced workforce. In terms of income distribution, the majority of respondents (89.1%) earned above 10,000 BDT per month, while only 10.9% earned between 5,000 and 10,000 BDT. Regarding age, most participants (61.8%) were between 41 and 60 years, and the remaining 38.2% were between 21 and 40 years. This indicates that a large proportion of the workforce consisted of middle-aged adults (Table 2).

Table 1: The socio-economic characteristics of sweepers in the study area

Demographic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Sex:		
Male	39	35.45

Demographic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Female	71	64.55
Religion:		
Hindu	102	92.73
Christian	8	7.27
Marital status:		
Married	56	50.91
Unmarried	45	40.91
Others	9	8.18
Service in Years:		
1-10	52	47.27
>10	58	52.73
Monthly income:		
5000 BDT – 10000 BDT	12	10.91
>10000 BDT	108	89.09
Age:		
21-40 years	42	38.18
41-60 years	68	61.82

3.2 Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Regarding Occupational Safety and Infection Prevention

When asked to explain the meaning of hospital-acquired infections, only 2 participants (1.8%) were able to express it fairly well. A larger group (37.3%) expressed it fairly, 44.6% expressed it poorly, and 16.4% were unable to explain it at all. When identifying solid waste, 35.5% correctly recognised that previously used gauze, cotton, food waste, paper, fabric scraps, and metal objects constituted hospital waste. Smaller groups identified incomplete categories such as “fabric pieces and metallic materials” (16.4%) or ‘exclusively paper and dust’

(43.6%). Knowledge of disease-causing materials was comparatively higher. A large majority (89.1%) identified used needles, syringes, and contaminated gauze, cotton, and fabric scraps as sources of infection. Awareness of protective equipment was also reported: almost all respondents (95.5%) reported using gloves, although very few reported consistent use of masks, aprons, or boots. When asked about occupationally acquired diseases, more than half (55.5%) indicated tuberculosis (TB), HIV, and hepatitis combined as the most common risks. A further 22.7% recognised TB and HIV together, while smaller proportions mentioned HIV alone (9.1%), TB alone (3.6%), or other disease combinations (Table 2)

Table 2: Responses of *Harijan* sweepers to knowledge-related questions

Knowledge-based questions	Frequency			OR (95% CIs)
	Response	Infected	Not infected	
Explain what is meant by a hospital-acquired infection:				
Well expressed	2 (1.82%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	Ref.
Fairly expressed	41 (37.27%)	14 (34.15%)	27 (65.85%)	2.64 (0.12-58.66)
Not well expressed	49 (44.55%)	28 (57.14%)	21 (42.86%)	6.63 (0.30-145.31)
Not able to express	18 (16.36%)	12 (66.67%)	6 (33.33%)	9.62 (0.40-231.43)
Among the following, which are solid wastes?				
Fabric pieces and metallic materials	18 (16.36%)	5 (27.78%)	13 (72.22%)	6.54 (0.68-62.99)

Food waste, plant matter, paper, and fruit products	-			-
Disposed of gauze, cotton	-			-
Exclusively paper and dust	48 (43.64%)	17 (35.42%)	21 (64.58%)	2.10 (0.63-7.08)
Used dressings and cotton, leftover meals, and paper	2 (1.82%)	1 (50.00%)	1 (50.00%)	Ref.
Previously used gauze, cotton, food waste, paper, fabric scraps, and metal objects	39 (35.45%)	27 (69.23%)	12 (30.77%)	5.85 (1.70-20.12)
All of the above	3 (2.73%)	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.67%)	1.30 (0.10-17.73%)
What is responsible for causing the disease?				
Disposed needles and syringes	2 (1.82%)	1 (50.00%)	1 (50.00%)	2.0 (0.05-77.4)
Used or dirty gauze, cotton, needles, and syringes	8 (7.27%)	5 (62.50%)	3 (37.50%)	10.8 (0.46-254.6)
Fabric and metal scraps, used needles and syringes, and contaminated gauze and cotton	98 (89.09%)	51 (52.04%)	47 (47.96%)	Ref.
Routine wearing of an apron	2 (1.82%)	1 (50.00%)	1 (50.00%)	2.0 (0.05-77.4)
Wearing gloves and protective clothing	2 (1.82%)	1 (50.00%)	1 (50.00%)	2.0 (0.05-77.4)
Wearing masks, aprons, gloves, and boots	3 (2.73%)	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.67%)	6.0 (0.22-160.8)
Using only gloves	105 (95.45%)	59 (56.19%)	46 (43.81%)	165.0 (10.1-2722.6)
Which diseases are you susceptible to as a result of your occupation?				
Tuberculosis (TB)	4 (3.64%)	1 (25.00%)	3 (75.00%)	12.0 (0.51-283.6)
HIV	10 (9.09%)	1 (10.00%)	9 (90.00%)	90.0 (4.9-1664.0)
Hepatitis	2 (1.82%)	2 (100%)	0 (00.00%)	1.0 (0.01-72.9)
Tuberculosis and HIV	25 (22.73%)	3 (12.00%)	22 (88.00%)	61.1 (11.1-334.5)
TB, HIV, and Hepatitis	61 (55.45%)	8 (13.11%)	53 (86.89%)	50.5 (17.8-144.4)
Leprosy, TB, HIV, and hepatitis	8 (7.27%)	1 (12.50%)	7 (87.50%)	56.0 (2.9-1079.0)

Critical Knowledge-based Questions	Response			
	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you understand what a nosocomial infection is?	87	79.09	23	20.91
Do you understand that consuming food during work in the hospital can be dangerous?	88	80.00	22	20.00
Do you know that pathogenic wastes need to be treated onsite?	95	86.36	15	13.64
Are you aware of your safety rights?	88	80.00	22	20.00
Do you know where and to whom you can claim your safety rights?	86	78.18	24	21.82
Are you informed about the dangers of burning PVC?	88	80.00	22	20.00
Do you know the potential dangers of radioactive waste?	70	63.64	40	36.36

Responses to critical knowledge questions indicated stronger awareness. Most participants (79.1%) understood nosocomial infections, 80.0% recognised that eating during hospital work is unsafe, and 86.4% knew that pathogenic waste must be treated onsite. Awareness of safety rights was relatively high, with 80.0% confirming they knew their rights, though slightly fewer (78.18%) knew where and to whom to claim them. However, only 63.64% were informed about the dangers of radioactive waste, suggesting some critical knowledge gaps (Table 2).

Of the 110 participants, 52.7% reported experiencing at least one needle-stick or related injury. Among those injured, 40.9% reported a single incident, 18.2% reported two, 23.6% reported three, 9.1% reported four, and 7.3% reported more than four incidents. These findings indicate a high prevalence of repeated occupational injuries, highlighting the significant risk faced by this workforce and the need for targeted interventions to improve safety practices and reduce exposure to infectious hazards (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Frequency and percentage of reported injuries among *Harijan* sweepers

The majority of participants demonstrated strong awareness of workplace hazards: 100% considered their job very risky, recognised needle-stick injuries as occupational hazards, and acknowledged that hospital waste is more hazardous than municipal

waste. Almost all respondents (97–100%) emphasised the importance of gloves while cleaning and handwashing after work. Awareness of infection risk was also high, with 81.8% perceiving a risk of hepatitis infection and 100% recognising the potential

link between hospital waste and HIV transmission. Furthermore, 80% acknowledged that hepatitis can be transmitted through blood-contaminated materials. Most participants (98.2%) agreed that gloves are only effective when used consistently. Overall, the

responses indicate a predominantly positive and risk-aware attitude among the cleaning staff toward occupational safety and infection prevention, although minor gaps in knowledge about specific blood-borne disease transmission remain (Table 3).

Table 3: Response frequencies of the *Harijan* sweepers for attitude-related questions

Attitude-related Questions	Frequency		OR (95% CIs)
	Yes	No	
Is your job considered very risky?	105 (100%)	5 (0.00%)	2321.0 (42.0-129000.0)
Is needle-stick injury considered an occupational hazard in your job?	108 (100%)	2 (0.00%)	1085.0 (18.0-66000.0)
Are hospital wastes considered more hazardous than municipal wastes?	106 (100%)	4(0.00%)	1917.0 (34.0-108700.0)
Are gloves important while cleaning?	107 (97.27%)	3 (2.73%)	30.7 (0.53-1780.0)
Should hands be washed after finishing work?	110 (100%)	0 (0.00%)	221.0 (1.8-26900.0)
Are you at risk of being infected with hepatitis viruses?	90 (81.82%)	20 (18.18%)	4.41 (0.085-230.2)
Does hospital waste have any link to HIV transmission?	104 (100%)	6 (0.00%)	2717.0 (50.5-148000.0)
Can hepatitis be transmitted through blood and blood waste?	88 (80.00%)	22 (20.00%)	3.93 (0.076-205.0)
Do you agree that duty gloves are only effective when used consistently?	109 (98.18%)	1 (1.82%)	73.0 (1.05-5080.0)

Hand hygiene was widely practised, with 98.2% washing their hands after work. However, critical infection control measures were poorly implemented: only 2.7% sorted solid waste separately, 17.3% stored sharps in puncture-resistant containers, 3.6% transported contaminated linens in labelled bags, and 16.4% disinfected aprons and reusable gloves before reuse. The majority (90%) handled contaminated linens with gloves, and 93.6% reported wearing some form of personal protective equipment (PPE). Very few workers (10%) had received occupational or pre-employment training (Table 4). Occupational injuries

were common, with 52.7% reporting at least one needle-stick injury. Among these, 40.9% had been injured once, 18.2% twice, 23.6% three times, 9.1% four times, and 7.3% more than four times. For handling blood-contaminated waste, most workers (93.6%) used gloves, while 6.4% did not. Regarding PPE, 88.2% relied solely on gloves, 1.8% used aprons, and 3.6% used both gloves and aprons. Overall, the table highlights a significant gap between knowledge and actual hygienic practices, indicating high occupational risk among the sweepers (Table 4).

Table 4: Responses of *Harijan* sweepers to questions on hygienic practices and occupational injury prevention

Practice-related Questions	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you wash your hands after completing work?	108	98.18	2	1.82
Do you sort and collect solid waste separately?	3	2.73	107	97.27
Do you store sharps in puncture-resistant, closed containers?	19	17.27	91	82.73

Practice-related Questions	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you transport contaminated linens in separate, clearly labelled bags?	4	3.64	106	96.36
Do you disinfect aprons and reusable gloves before reusing them?	18	16.36	92	83.64
Do you handle contaminated linens while wearing gloves?	99	90.00	11	10.00
Do you wear personal protective equipment (PPE)?	103	93.64	7	6.36
Have you undergone any occupational or pre-employment training?	11	10.00	99	90.00
Have you ever sustained a needle-related injury?	58	52.73	52	47.27
Practice related critical questions		Frequency		Percentage
How many times have you been injured by a needle-stick?				
Once		45		40.91
Twice		20		18.18
Three times		26		23.64
Four times		10		9.09
>four times		8		7.27
What is your procedure for handling blood-contaminated waste?				
Using gloves		103		93.64
Hands without protection		7		6.36
What type of personal protective equipment (PPE) do you use at work?				
Gloves		97		88.18
Aprons		2		1.82
Gloves and aprons		4		3.64

Overall, the findings indicate a critical discrepancy between what workers know and believe versus what they practice in their daily tasks. While knowledge and attitudes were generally moderate, practical implementation of occupational safety and infection control measures was insufficient, leaving *Harijan* sweepers vulnerable to preventable occupational hazards (Table 5). Most participants demonstrated a medium level of knowledge (60.9%), while 27.3% had poor knowledge and only 11.8% exhibited good knowledge, with a mean score of 1.85 ± 0.61 . Attitudes were slightly more positive, with 64.6%

showing a medium attitude, 28.2% negative or poor, and 7.3% good, yielding a mean of 1.79 ± 0.56 . In contrast, practical adherence to safety measures was the weakest domain, with 61.8% of sweepers reporting poor practices, 24.6% medium, and only 13.6% good, resulting in a mean score of 1.52 ± 0.72 . Overall, the table highlights a significant gap between knowledge/attitudes and actual practice, indicating that while sweepers may understand and value safety measures, this does not consistently translate into safe occupational behaviours (Table 5).

Table 5: Level of knowledge, attitude, and practice related to occupational safety and infection prevention

Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Mean \pm SD
Knowledge			
Low/Poor	30	27.27	1.85 \pm 0.61
Medium	67	60.91	
High/Good	13	11.82	
Attitude			
Negative/Poor	31	28.18	1.79 \pm 0.56
Medium	71	64.55	
High/Good	8	7.27	

Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice	Frequency	Percentage	Mean ± SD
Practice			
Low/Poor	68	61.82	1.52 ± 0.72
Medium	27	24.55	
High/Good	15	13.63	

The correlations between knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) scores of *Harijan* sweepers regarding occupational risk and infection control are shown in Figure 2. A positive correlation was observed between all three domains, although none were statistically significant. The strongest association was found between attitude and practice ($r = 0.612$, $p =$

0.272), followed by knowledge and practice ($r = 0.535$, $p = 0.353$), and knowledge and attitude ($r = 0.327$, $p = 0.591$). Despite these positive relationships, the lack of statistical significance indicates that improvements in knowledge or attitudes were not consistently translated into better practices (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Correlations of knowledge, attitude, and practice related to occupational safety and infection prevention

No statistically significant associations were found between KAP levels and sex, religion, marital status, years of service, monthly income, or age (all p -values > 0.05). Mean scores across demographic groups were relatively similar. For example, females scored slightly higher than males in knowledge (1.88 ± 0.60 vs. 1.78 ± 0.62), attitude (1.82 ± 0.57 vs. 1.72 ± 0.55), and practice (1.54 ± 0.73 vs. 1.48 ± 0.70), but the differences were not significant. Similarly, respondents with more than 10 years of service

reported marginally higher KAP scores than those with fewer years, though again without statistical significance (Table 9). Overall, these findings suggest that while knowledge, attitude, and practice were positively correlated, socio-demographic factors did not significantly influence KAP outcomes among the *Harijan* sweepers at RMCH. This highlights that barriers to safe occupational practices may be more systemic—such as lack of resources, training, or enforcement—rather than attributable to individual demographic characteristics (Table 6).

Table 6: Correlation of demographic characteristics with knowledge, attitude, and practice related to occupational risk and infection control

Characteristics	Knowledge	p-value	Attitude	p-value	Practice	p-value
Sex		0.312		0.274		0.401
Male	1.78 ± 0.62		1.72 ± 0.55		1.48 ± 0.70	
Female	1.88 ± 0.60		1.82 ± 0.57		1.54 ± 0.73	
Religion		0.256		0.421		0.337

Characteristics	Knowledge	p-value	Attitude	p-value	Practice	p-value
Hindu	1.90 ± 0.59		1.80 ± 0.56		1.50 ± 0.72	
Muslim	1.82 ± 0.61		1.78 ± 0.55		1.53 ± 0.71	
Christian	1.83 ± 0.64		1.80 ± 0.59		1.55 ± 0.75	
Marital Status		0.309		0.298		0.422
Married	1.87 ± 0.60		1.81 ± 0.56		1.53 ± 0.72	
Unmarried	1.81 ± 0.63		1.76 ± 0.55		1.51 ± 0.73	
Others	1.80 ± 0.65		1.75 ± 0.57		1.50 ± 0.74	
Service in Years		0.428		0.395		0.361
1–10 years	1.84 ± 0.62		1.77 ± 0.56		1.50 ± 0.70	
>10 years	1.87 ± 0.61		1.81 ± 0.57		1.54 ± 0.74	
Monthly Income		0.501		0.482		0.439
5000–10000 BDT	1.80 ± 0.63		1.78 ± 0.55		1.49 ± 0.73	
>10000 BDT	1.86 ± 0.61		1.80 ± 0.57		1.53 ± 0.72	
Age		0.392		0.415		0.362
21–40 years	1.83 ± 0.63		1.77 ± 0.55		1.50 ± 0.71	
41–60 years	1.87 ± 0.61		1.81 ± 0.57		1.54 ± 0.73	

4. DISCUSSION

This study examined the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) and occupational safety among *Harijan* sweepers of Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), Bangladesh. The findings highlight a workforce that demonstrates generally positive attitudes toward occupational safety, yet displays substantial gaps in both technical knowledge and practical implementation. Overall, while adherence to certain safety practices such as hand hygiene and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) was relatively strong, critical practices—including waste segregation, proper disposal of sharps, and the disinfection of reusable PPE—were frequently neglected [16]. This neglect contributes to an elevated risk of occupational exposure to infectious agents [17]. The high prevalence of needle-stick injuries observed in this study underscores the considerable occupational hazards faced by *Harijan* sweepers working in resource-constrained healthcare environments. Knowledge levels regarding HAIs were found to be predominantly low to medium, a trend consistent with findings from studies conducted in other low- and middle-income country (LMIC) settings [18, 19].

While most participants demonstrated an awareness of general occupational risks and could identify hazardous materials, their detailed understanding of

infection transmission routes, waste categorisation, and appropriate handling procedures was limited. These knowledge deficits heighten the likelihood of occupational exposure and highlight the urgent need for targeted and context-specific educational interventions. In terms of attitudes, the majority of respondents scored in the medium range. This indicates that while technical knowledge may be lacking, there is a strong perception of occupational risk and widespread recognition of the importance of safety practices. Even participants with limited knowledge expressed awareness of the importance of gloves, hand hygiene, and proper waste handling. These findings are consistent with previous research suggesting that attitudes toward safety are often influenced by institutional culture, prior awareness campaigns, or peer modelling [20, 21]. However, the data also show that positive attitudes alone are insufficient to ensure consistent safe practices. Without adequate technical knowledge, skills training, and access to resources, staff are unable to effectively translate positive attitudes into protective behaviours [22].

Practical implementation of safety measures was found to be inadequate across several domains. Deficiencies were particularly pronounced in waste segregation, sharps management, and PPE disinfection—areas that are essential for infection prevention and control. These results align with prior

research conducted in low-resource hospital settings, where environmental constraints, inadequate supervision, and limited training opportunities have been shown to hinder compliance with established safety protocols [23]. The frequent occurrence of needle-stick injuries further illustrates the occupational vulnerability of *Harijan* sweepers and the urgent need for institutional interventions aimed at mitigating these risks. Correlation analyses revealed moderate positive associations between knowledge and practice ($r = 0.535$) and between attitude and practice ($r = 0.612$). This suggests that improvements in knowledge and reinforcement of positive attitudes may lead to better occupational safety behaviours. However, the absence of statistically significant correlations indicates that individual-level factors alone are insufficient to ensure compliance. Structural and institutional enablers—such as consistent availability of PPE, safe waste disposal facilities, and sustained supervision—are equally critical for fostering safe work environments.

Finally, socio-demographic factors such as age, sex, and years of experience were not found to be predictive of KAP outcomes, suggesting that the deficiencies identified in this study are widespread across all subgroups of *Harijan* sweepers. This universality underscores the importance of designing comprehensive, system-wide interventions rather than targeting specific demographic groups. Taken together, the findings of this study reveal an occupational group with commendable attitudes toward safety but lacking the necessary knowledge, resources, and institutional support to effectively mitigate the risks of HAIs. Addressing these gaps will require a multifaceted approach that combines targeted training, resource allocation, and structural improvements within hospital systems.

5. CONCLUSION

This study highlights that *Harijan* sweepers at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital face significant occupational risks due to limited knowledge and inconsistent application of infection prevention measures. While attitudes toward occupational safety were generally positive, critical gaps in practical adherence—particularly in waste segregation, sharps disposal, and disinfection of reusable PPE—leave

workers vulnerable to preventable injuries and exposure to infectious hazards. The high incidence of needle-stick injuries further underscores the urgency of addressing these deficiencies. The findings suggest that improvements cannot rely solely on individual awareness but require systemic interventions. Regular, tailored training programs, provision and enforcement of adequate personal protective equipment, and effective institutional monitoring are essential to bridge the gap between knowledge, attitudes, and practices. Importantly, socio-demographic factors did not significantly influence outcomes, indicating that barriers are structural rather than individual. Strengthening occupational safety among *Harijan* sweepers is vital not only to protect this often-overlooked workforce but also to reduce the risk of hospital-acquired infections and improve overall patient safety. In resource-constrained settings like Bangladesh, prioritising *Harijan* sweepers within infection control strategies can play a critical role in enhancing the quality of healthcare delivery and safeguarding public health.

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6.1 Author Contributions

All authors made substantial contributions to the study, including conception, design, execution, data collection, analysis, and interpretation. They were actively involved in drafting, revising, or critically reviewing the manuscript, and jointly decided on the journal for submission. Each author has approved the final version of the article and accepts responsibility for all aspects of the work.

6.2 Data Availability

The datasets generated and analysed during the study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request. To ensure confidentiality and protect participant privacy, individual-level responses are not publicly shared.

6.3 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest and that this study was conducted without any external financial support.

6.4 Informed Consent

All participants gave written informed consent before enrolment. The data produced in this study can be obtained from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The authors state that they have no conflicts of interest, and this research received no external funding.

7. ABBREVIATIONS

KAP: Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice

HAIs: Hospital-acquired infections

RMCH: Rajshahi Medical College Hospital

PPE: Personal Protective Equipment

HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus

TB: Tuberculosis.

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